

FAIRSFair

Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe

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Searching for research data can be cumbersome. What terms should we search for? Is the content of these datasets actually possible to combine or compare and in that case, how? If we want the “machine to know what we mean” we need to clear a few hurdles:

1. We should make sure that when two data files are “talking about the same thing”, they ideally use the same way to do that. If that is not possible, we need to be explicit that two different terms or identifiers are the same. There are deeper difficulties with this that are out of the scope of this document to address: researchers may differ in opinion about whether two things are “the same” or not, depending on the context of what they are researching. See e.g Bachelor et al 2014.

2. We should make sure that it is obvious when two data files are “talking about different things”, i.e. we should avoid ambiguity.
3. We need to make sure to explicitly describe every anomaly that could be present in the data. For example, it should be documented whether a missing data value means that the value has been determined to be empty, that it has not been measured or that its value is unknown or irrelevant.
4. We need to make sure that no guesswork is needed to interpret relationships between data items. For example, in a data table listing: patients, their illness, and medication they are taking. A human user can *assume* that the medication is taken in an attempt to cure or mitigate the illness; semantic interoperability demands that this relation is explicitly described, so a machine can also use it.

Making meaning sense for machines

Solutions for semantic interoperability do the following:

1. Rather than using a *term* to describe something that is specific to a human language and may be context-dependent in practice, they prefer to refer to *concepts* that are represented by a unique *identifier*.
2. Each data value is associated with a precise *data type*, documented to such precision that misunderstandings are avoided.

Interoperability, the third letter of FAIR, is commonly considered the most difficult one to achieve. Proper interoperability can save a lot of time in research because it minimises misunderstandings and also makes it much easier to combine datasets coming from different sources: either similar datasets joined together to make a larger study, or dissimilar datasets that are joined together to solve complex problems.

Interoperability needs to address both the format in which data is stored, and the description of the data (all the data elements) in a way that makes sure that it can be interpreted by others, even in 10 years.

This requires

- adequate at least partly machine readable metadata in catalogues or within the dataset or file
- consistent use of semantic artefacts like controlled vocabularies that are shared and understood within the scientific community. They should be documented and maintained.
- consistent use of open standards for data formats, flexible enough to accommodate the variety of data expected, and on the other hand documented enough that every aspect of the data is clarified without leaving any ambiguity.
- all values have to be associated with data types and numeric values have explicit units, and the meaning of a missing or an out of range data value is defined
- relations between data items are explicit (e.g. a “temperature” is the temperature of the given “object”, and not of the environment)

Technology to support semantic interoperability

The original paper describing the FAIR principles carefully avoided choosing a single technology to implement them. It can be seen, however, that research communities that are currently the furthest along the road to implement interoperability for FAIR data have often chosen Linked Data technologies (recognized by abbreviations like RDF, OWL, SKOS, SPARQL). This is not because this solution is the only approach that could be taken, but because it has been under development for many years and is currently one of the few frameworks that can make data unambiguously understandable. It is possible that the role played by Linked Data today could be played by another more powerful approach in the future, but Linked Data has the best potential for implementing FAIR interoperability at this moment.

The core of Linked Data is formed by the Resource Description Framework (RDF). All data represented in RDF is turned into so-called “semantic triples” that each contain a statement in the form of subject-predicate-object, each describing either a property of something (subject: “bird” predicate: “body temperature in degrees C” object: “41”) or a relation between two things (subject: “Alice” predicate: “Talks to” object: “Bob”). In order to make these statements machine readable in RDF, subjects and predicates are never just a character string, but always an Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI). The objects in an RDF triple can either be a IRI, literal or blank node, and if it is a literal then there are techniques to make sure it is well described; e.g. the language of a string is explicitly added. To represent knowledge, multiple RDF triples are put together in a network or “graph”.

A common misconception about Linked Data is that it requires all data to be represented as RDF. In fact, RDF is a very inefficient way of storing and processing many forms of dense data. The requirement that is placed upon us for interoperability is not that the data is all converted to RDF, but that someone *skilled in the field* would be able to set up an automated process to perform that conversion fully automatically. However, it should be noticed that if data must still be interoperable in 10 years, that either requires that there will still be people available at that time who are *skilled in the field*, or, alternatively, that the automated process for the conversion is actually built. In practice, dense tabular research data is often left as such, and combined with abstracted conclusions and metadata represented as RDF.

When using Linked Data, the IRIs for related things are stored in collections, which are named differently depending on the structure and how the relationships are described. They can be named as glossary, controlled vocabulary, thesaurus, ontology or data model. All of these can together be called “semantic artefacts”.

Many of the complexities in the implementation of RDF arise from its flexibility. Software that uses the data often makes assumptions about a data structure. Tabular data makes this easy because it enforces this structure. For RDF, a structure is more difficult to guarantee, and data structure validation is provided separately. One modern example of a technique used for this is the Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL). SHACL writes simple statements (in RDF!) about data that describes the structure of that data. It allows matching a *data graph*

with a *shapes graph*. This way, SHACL makes it possible to describe what properties and relationships the nodes in the graph must have and must not have, use this to filter the graph, and raise an error when conditions are not met. If there is no error, software querying the graph can be sure that it satisfies the structure it needs.

Dos

- Get support from data stewards in finding good practice and solutions that serve your scientific needs.
- Pay attention to data, metadata, formats and data documentation already when planning your research. Try to make your data management FAIR by design and data born FAIR. (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>)
- Re-use existing schemas and vocabularies whenever possible.
- Document all metadata and data elements, e.g. from which vocabulary they are.
- Follow existing formats and standards, prefer open, documented and machine accessible.
- If you create own formats or concepts, see that they are made available in a FAIR (machine readable and interoperable) manner, for variables e.g. CDI-DDI (<https://ddialliance.org/Specification/ddi-cdi>), regarding semantic artefacts learn more, e.g. Recommendations for FAIR semantics (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6276576>).
- Consider making your data available as linked open data (Deep FAIR)
- Give feedback to service providers when data models or vocabularies don't serve your needs. Help define and develop ontologies.

Don'ts

- Don't create your own variables, terms or definitions unless you really have to.
- Don't create your own formats, data types or schemas unless necessary.
- Don't use terms, codes and standards in a way that can be misunderstood.

References

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